

MODELING AND OPTIMIZATION OF CUTTING FORCES DURING MACHINING OF AISI D2 STEEL

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ABSTRACT: *Manufacturing at effective cost and ease is the prime aim of every industry. With high cost of cutting tool, one of the primary objectives in machining is to minimize the cutting force that helps in reducing tool wear. To keep away the harmful effects of coolant, the current work deals with a machining operation in two conditions, i.e. in dry environment and air-cooling environment. For predicting cutting force variation, the present work developed a mathematical model with response surface methodology (RSM) method in turning hardened AISI D2 steel. From analysis of variance (ANOVA), feed and depth of cut are the influential parameters that control the cutting force in both dry environment and air-cooling environment. The RSM model can predict the cutting force with accuracies 89.73% and 89.68% respectively. Using response optimization technique, the minimum cutting force obtained as 44.5 N and 64.7 N in dry turning and air-cooled turning respectively. The optimized confirmatory test showed error less than 5% signifies that the developed model can be effectively used in the turning operation*

KEYWORDS: *cutting force, dry turning, air-cooled turning, RSM, ANOVA, optimization*

1 INTRODUCTION

The effective use of cutting parameter combination in manufacturing operation is a key factor for optimum output. In every industry, the main motive is to produce product with low cost and optimum product performance. The cutting tool experiences a strong cutting force during hard machining, which results in a high rate of tool wear. High-grade cutting tools like carbide, ceramic, CBN, PCBN etc. is generally applied for hardened materials machining. But this high-grade cutting tool is very costly. The effective implementation of cutting tool during machining is key factor from the point of cost as well as easiness. Therefore, the optimization of the cutting parameter in such a scenario is much helpful. Due to excessive heat at the cutting tool-workpiece juncture, coolants are generally used to remove the heat. But these coolants are toxic and hazardous to the health of the operator, moreover the disposal of the coolants also create the environment pollution. With this concern, researchers are trying to develop some environment friendly techniques such as vegetable-based oil, minimum quantity lubrication (MQL), cryogenic cooling etc. The method somewhat proves to be environment friendly, but the cost of the oils is also a concern along with its disposal. Recently, novel air-cooling technique is being introduced during hard

machining. Air is freely available in nature and it can be compressed and injected into tool workpiece junction which is cost-effective also. Several researches have been done to use different environment favorable machining techniques for better machinability. Using a mixed oxide ceramic insert, Sarma and Dixit differentiated dry and air-cooling machining of grey cast iron [1]. They observed that the tool wear, surface roughness, machining forces were lesser in air-cooling machining in comparison to dry environment. The effects of two distinct nano-fluids, alumina and Molybdenum sulphide (MoS₂), in hard turning of AISI 304 stainless steel were observed by Sharma et al. [2]. RSM method was adopted for analysis of the experiments. Using Al-MoS₂ hybrid nano-cutting fluid, they observed minimization in machining forces and improvement in surface finish in comparison to Al₂O₃ mixed nanofluid. Gunay et al. noticed the influence of carbide inserts in hard machining of Nimonic 80A in the environment of dry, air-cooling and oil-spraying [3]. Tool life and surface integrity was enhanced using oil-spray at speed- 60 m/min. Gajrani et al. differentiated the influence of minimum quantity of cutting fluid (MQCF) and flooded coolant with respect to different performance parameters in machining hardened AISI H-13 steel [4]. Surface roughness, friction coefficient, and machining forces all

decreased using MQCF in comparison to flooded coolant. Kumar et al. observed the influence of spray coolant during machining hardened AISI D2 steel [5]. They carried out ANN modeling to forecast the behavior of flank wear and chip reduction coefficient. They observed that while chip reduction coefficient improved with increased depth of cut, flank wear improved with increased speed and depth of cut. Using ANN modeling, both flank wear and chip reduction coefficient was predicted with less error. Sarikaya and Gullu utilised Taguchi method and RSM during CNC turning of AISI 1050 steel with minimum quantity lubrication [6]. They observed feed rate and cooling method were the significant parameters for surface roughness. The formulated modeling can predict surface roughness with greater accuracy. Singh et al. compared dry and MQL method in turning hardened EN 31 steel [7]. They used Topsis method to optimize the machining factors. Using MQL, it was observed that surface finish improved, cutting temperature lowered and chip reduction coefficient improved as compared to dry turning. Using TOPSIS method, the best parametric settings of the experiments were v - 196 m/min, f - 0.088 mm/rev for MQL condition. Sivalingam et al. studied the performance of environment beneficial machining with atomized spray cutting fluid during turning Inconel 718 alloy [8]. RSM was applied for prediction of the response. The performance of atomized spray cutting fluid (ASCF) was related with dry turning. Surface finish was improved by 17-34%, vibration acceleration reduced by 14-29% using ASCF as compared to dry turning. Using ASCF, the tool wear in terms of abrasion and chipping also reduced due to the lubricating effect of spray cooling. Sharma et al. observed the influence of nano-cutting technique by amalgamation of alumina with multi walled carbon nanoparticles in various volume concentrations [9]. They observed that by the rise of carbon nanoparticle concentration, the tool wear was minimized. Alumina multi-walled carbon nanotube cutting fluid showed lower cutting forces and surface roughness than alumina nano-cutting fluid. Lalwani et al. observed the usefulness of machining factors for different cutting forces and surface finish in hard machining MDN250 steel [10]. Experimental settings were run using RSM with central composite design. Depth of cut was the effective factor for feed force, feed rate and depth of cut for thrust forces and feed rate and depth of cut for cutting forces. Linear model was found suitable in case of machining forces in consideration to feed and depth of cut. Non-linear quadratic model was found suitable for surface roughness. Bagaber and Yusoff studied the energy and cost saving analysis in a turning operation using

RSM and genetic algorithm II (NSGA II) [11]. Using RSM, energy can be saved by 9.2% and the machining expenses were minimized by 4.6%. By applying second generation results of optimization with NSGA II, the results were improved by 70% as compared to RSM. Joshi et al. compared the performance of dry; MQL and flooded cooling on responses surface finish and flank wear [12]. They have prepared two MQL solutions, MQL1 (150 ml/h) and MQL2 (230 ml/h). The experimental analysis confirmed that using MQL, surface finish and flank wear were better comparing to dry and flooded cooling. The effect of MQL2 was more beneficial than MQL1. Zaman and Dhar investigated the effect of double jet nozzle for delivering MQL with an attempt to improve the machinability during a turning operation [13]. The machining performances were compared with a single jet MQL and dry turning. The performance of double jet MQL machining was found superior as compared using single jet MQL machining and dry machining. Gajrani et al. analyzed the effect of minimum quantity cutting fluid (MQCF) with environment friendly concept and compared it with flooded cooling and in dry atmosphere in hard turned AISI H-13 steel [14]. Machining forces, friction coefficient and surface roughness were minimized by optimization of MQCF parameters. The machining performances were also improved with the using of MQCF technique in comparison to flooded coolant and dry atmosphere.

From the above literature survey, it is observed that lot of works have been done with different cooling environments, especially minimum quantity lubrication; vegetable oil based cooling, different nano-fluids cooling, cryogenic cooling etc. But these methods have high cost and set up is also a tedious work. The air-cooling method is not so much costly as compared to these methods as air is compressed through a compressor and it is supplied at a required pressure to the cutting zone. Air is freely available on nature, so the cost of the method is also low and moreover it is completely environment friendly. Also, the cutting force analysis has been done less as compared to other performance parameters viz. surface roughness, flank wear etc. during machining hardened steel. Generally, in hard turning operations, coolants are used to remove the heat at tool-workpiece zone. The novelty of the work is that two environment friendly methods viz. dry and air-cooling is utilized which remove the use of harmful effects of chemical coolants in hard turning. With this concern, the present work is performed using compressed air in turning hardened AISI D2 steel and its performance is compared with another environment friendly technique, i.e. in dry

atmosphere for response cutting force to see the machining behavior.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DATA

The workpiece AISI D2 steel is hardened to 50 HRC in a furnace (Make: Voltam Furnace Industries, Model: VFI-1400). Maximum temperature is 1400°C. The turning experiments were conducted in a lathe, power- 5.5 kW and the spindle speed 40-2300 rpm (Make: Tussor Machine Tools India Pvt. Ltd., Model: SC250). The cutting force (range 0-10 kN) is analyzed with a dynamometer (Make: Kistler, Model: 9257B). The cutting force range is 0-10 kN. To get the compressed air, reciprocating air compressor (Make: Elgi, Model: TS03HN) with power 3 HP and a maximum pressure of 12 Kg/cm². The rate of flow and the pressure of the compressed air towards the nozzle end are 0.00043 m³/sec and 1.1 bar respectively. The cutting tool is coated carbide insert (Make: Sandvik, Model: SNMG 12 04 08-KM3215). Fig.1 shows the experimental set up where dynamometer, workpiece, compressed air delivery, tool post has been shown in a single picture.

Fig. 1 Experimental set up

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this part, the values of the hard turning operation are analyzed with RSM method. The three cutting parameters are considered for the experiment, viz. cutting speed (v) in m/min, feed rate (f) in mm/rev and depth of cut (d) in mm. The turning operation is performed under two conditions, dry turning (DT) and air-cooled turning (ACT). The response is cutting force (CF). Each cutting parameter has three levels. Using full factorial design, total 27 numbers are conducted. The experiment has been replicated three times because of the variation of machining behavior and the mean value is considered. Table 1 shows the cutting factors and its level. Table 2 shows the cutting force value in

DT and ACT along with their full factorial settings. In general, from table 2, it is noticed that the cutting force is less in DT comparing to ACT. The reason of less cutting force in DT can be explained as follows: During DT, the heat generation at the cutting tool-workpiece junction is high because of severe friction. This high temperature during machining helps the workpiece becoming softer due to heat which results in less cutting force. The same phenomenon is not happened in case of ACT. The RSM technique has been applied for finding a relationship with respect to the cutting parameters and the response for better prediction accuracy. Commercial software Minitab 17 is considered for the RSM analysis.

Table 1. Cutting parameters and its level

Parameters	Level		
	Low	Medium	High
v (m/min)	100	125	150
f (mm/rev)	0.05	0.10	0.15
d (mm)	0.25	0.40	0.55

Table 2: Experimental settings with cutting force values

Expt. No	Parameters			Cutting force (N)	
	v (m/min)	f (mm/rev)	d (mm)	DT	ACT
1	100	0.05	0.25	50	70
2	100	0.05	0.40	93	100
3	100	0.05	0.55	135	120
4	100	0.10	0.25	85	92
5	100	0.10	0.40	172	225
6	100	0.10	0.55	238	245
7	100	0.15	0.25	110	124
8	100	0.15	0.40	180	210
9	100	0.15	0.55	182	240
10	125	0.05	0.25	74	89
11	125	0.05	0.40	105	135
12	125	0.05	0.55	162	183
13	125	0.10	0.25	109	115
14	125	0.10	0.40	158	128
15	125	0.10	0.55	259	289
16	125	0.15	0.25	120	130
17	125	0.15	0.40	172	180
18	125	0.15	0.55	245	272
19	150	0.05	0.25	78	86
20	150	0.05	0.40	106	110
21	150	0.05	0.55	135	189
22	150	0.10	0.25	57	73
23	150	0.10	0.40	140	155
24	150	0.10	0.55	187	230
25	150	0.15	0.25	59	80
26	150	0.15	0.40	150	170
27	150	0.15	0.55	270	301

3.1 Analysis of results by RSM Analysis of cutting force in DT

RSM is a statistical analysis technique that uses regression equation to find the optimum response values through prediction. In RSM, the experimental data's are analyzed with respect to condition of the response, viz. maximum or minimum. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) table obtained from RSM can signify the effect of a factor with respect to its response. In ANOVA, parameter having P value 0.05 or less than 0.05 is considered to be significant. P value excess of 0.05 is considered as insignificant. Table 3 shows the ANOVA for cutting force in dry turning (DT). Quadratic model is used for analyzing the results in RSM it can predict more accurately as compared to the linear and square model. From the table, it is noticed that the linear term feed rate (f) and depth of cut (d) are influential as P<0.05. The square term, interaction between (v*v) and (f*f) are found as influential. The regression model from the RSM analysis for cutting force in DT is found as 89.73% accurate. The modelling formulation of cutting force in DT is presented as

$$Cutting\ force\ (DT) = -497 + 7.7v + 1810f - 51d - 0.0339v * v - 8533f * f + 7d * d - 2.27v * f + 1.96v * d + 1978f * d.....(1)$$

The equation (1) is found to be valid for any values of v, f, d within its lower and upper limits. Fig. 2 depicts the main effect graph of cutting force in DT. The graph shows that cutting force is increasing linearly by the rise of feed and depth of cut. But the influence of depth of cut is highly prominent in comparison to feed which is observed from Fig. 2. But cutting speed's effect on cutting force is very less as observed from Fig. 2. The interaction plots are not drawn as interaction factors have less effect on the response.

Fig 2: Main effect plot of cutting force in DT

Table 3: ANOVA analysis of cutting force in DT

Source	D F	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value	Significant
Model	9	89551.6	9950.2	16.51	0.00	Yes
Linear	3	80750.6	26916.9	44.66	0.00	Yes
v	1	220.5	220.5	0.37	0.55	No
f	1	16805.6	16805.6	27.88	0.00	Yes
d	1	63724.5	63724.5	105.72	0.00	Yes
Square	3	5419.0	1806.3	3.00	0.06	Yes
v*v	1	2688.2	2688.2	4.46	0.05	No
f*f	1	2730.7	2730.7	4.53	0.05	No
d*d	1	0.2	0.2	0.00	0.98	No
2-way interaction	3	3382.0	1127.7	1.87	0.17	No
v*f	1	96.3	96.3	0.16	0.69	No
v*d	1	645.3	645.3	1.07	0.31	No
f*d	1	2640.3	2640.3	4.38	0.05	No
Error	17	602.8	602.8			
Total	26	99798.7				

Analysis of cutting force in ACT

The cutting force analysis is also performed in ACT. The ANOVA analysis of cutting force in ACT is presented in Table 4. The table shows that feed and depth of cut are dominant parameters because P<0.05. Other factors are observed as insignificant because P>0.05. The regression formulation from the RSM analysis for cutting force in ACT is found as 89.68% accurate. The modelling formulation of cutting force in ACT is presented as

$$Cutting\ force\ (ACT) = -216 + 4.21v + 2047f - 461d - 0.0197v * v - 7000f * f + 252d * d - 7.87v * f + 3.60v * d + 2578f * d.....(2)$$

The equation (2) is found to be valid for any values of v, f, d within its lower and upper limits. Fig. 3 depicts the main effect plots of cutting force in ACT. The plot shows that cutting force is increasing linearly by rise in feed and depth of cut. But the influence of depth of cut is highly prominent in comparison to feed rate which is observed from Fig. 3. Cutting speed has virtually little effect on cutting force. The accuracy of the model can be predicted by investigation of the residuals. Residuals are the discrepancy between the expected values and the calculated experimental values. This can be found by plotting the normal probability plot versus the residuals and through the residuals vs the predicting values. For adequacy of the model, the residual points should form a straight line on the normal probability plot. On the other case the plotting of the residuals vs the predicting values should not form

any type of structure and no specific shape. Figures 4 and 5, respectively, show the normal probability plotting and the plotting of residuals against the expected values of cutting force in DT. Figure 4 shows that the residuals are linear, indicating that the errors are positioned regularly. Figure 5 shows that there are no specific patterns or structure. This means that the proposed model is admissible and that neither the independence assumption nor the constant variance assumption should be questioned [7]. Similar to this, Figs. 6 and 7 respectively illustrate the normal probability plotting and the plotting of residuals vs the expected values of cutting force in ACT. The justification of Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 is somewhat similar with Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Fig 3: Main effect plot of cutting force in ACT

Quadratic regression models are adopted in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 for both DT and ACT to predict the cutting force behaviour. These quadratic models developed here can predict the cutting force more accurately than linear and square models. The regression equation developed here can be used to predict cutting forces for any parametric combinations within the limit of the cutting range for the present work. Based on the accuracy, the developed equation can be implemented in industrial applications also for the current parameter settings.

Table 4: ANOVA analysis of cutting force in ACT

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value	Significant
Model	9	113873	12652.5	16.42	0.000	Yes
Linear	3	103097	34365.7	44.59	0.000	Yes
v	1	57	57	0.07	0.789	No
f	1	21701	21701	28.16	0.000	Yes
d	1	81339	81339	105.54	0.000	Yes
Square	3	2943	980.9	1.27	0.315	No
v*v	1	913	912.7	1.18	0.292	No
f*f	1	1837	1837.5	2.38	0.141	No
d*d	1	193	192.7	0.25	0.623	No
2-way interaction	3	7833	2610.9	3.39	0.042	Yes
v*f	1	1160	1160.3	1.51	0.237	No
v*d	1	2187	2187	2.84	0.110	No
f*d	1	4485	4485	5.82	0.027	Yes

Error	17	13102	770.7			
Total	26	126975				

Fig 4: Normal probability plot of the residual for CF (DT)

Fig 5: Plot of residual versus fitting values of CF (DT)

Fig 6: Normal probability plot of the residual for CF (ACT)

Fig 7: Plot of residual versus fitting values of CF (ACT)

The 3D surface plots of cutting force in DT and ACT is depicted in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 respectively. As cutting speed is not significant for cutting force in both DT and ACT, so the 3D surface plot is drawn between feed rate and depth of cut and the corresponding cutting force value is plotted. The 3D surface plot graph is drawn keeping cutting speed value constant at 125 m/min for both DT and ACT. Figure 8 shows that with a fixed cutting speed, the cutting force in DT increases by increasing feed rate and depth of cut. Similar type of observation is noticed in Fig. 9 also. The rise in material removal rate with higher feed rates and deeper cuts is the cause of the increased cutting force. Due to high feed and large depth of cut, the tool has to travel through a depth inside the workpiece that gets resisted by the workpiece, finally leading to a high cutting force. Figures 10 and 11 show the contour plot for cutting force in DT and ACT respectively for a constant cutting speed 125 m/min. It can be seen from these two plots that, at a constant cutting speed, cutting force increases as feed rate and depth of cut rise. The observation in Figs. 10 and 11 are found to be similar with Figs. 8 and 9 respectively. This means the observation obtained for cutting force in DT and ACT from 3D surface plot is in line with the contour plot. Thus Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 can be considered as an expert system for predicting cutting forces in DT and ACT at a constant cutting speed for any values of feed and depth of cut within the domain of the cutting conditions.

Fig 8: 3D surface plot for cutting force in DT at v =125 m/min

Fig 9: 3D surface plot for cutting force in ACT at v =125 m/min

Fig 10: Contour plot for cutting force in DT at v =125 m/min

Fig 11: Contour plot for cutting force in ACT at v =125 m/min

One of the most important criteria in machining is the reduction of tool wear. As tool wear is considered as inevitable criteria in machining, so the choice of the cutting factors plays a significant part regarding this. The tool wear will be lesser if the tool tip experiences less cutting force. So, the important criteria are to do machining in such a way as to get less cutting force which create less wear on the cutting tool. Keeping view on this, response surface optimization technique which is one of the best methods for obtaining optimal parametric combinations during machining is used. In this case, the main aim is to minimize the cutting force. In Fig. 12 and Table 5, respectively, the RSM's findings for the ideal cutting parameters are presented. The optimal cutting parameter is cutting speed- 150 m/min, feed rate- 0.05 mm/rev, depth of cut- 0.25 mm. The optimum value of cutting force in DT and ACT are found as 44.6 N and 64.7 N respectively as shown in table 5.

Fig 12: Response surface optimization of cutting force

Table 5: Response optimizer setup for cutting force in DT and ACT

Response	Goal	Lower	Target	Upper	Predicted	Desirability
CF (DT)	Minimize	50	70	270	44.5	1
CF (ACT)	Minimize	70	70	301	64.7	1

3.2 Confirmation Test

For confirming the prediction precision of the developed model, three confirmatory experiments are conducted as shown in Table 6 for DT and Table 7 for ACT respectively as a confirmatory test within the range of the level of the cutting parameters. The results of experiments and predictions were found to be more accurate and closer together, which can be taken into account for machining. The deviation between experimental and prediction value is less than 5%. This demonstrates that the formulated modelling can be applied to predict the cutting force for any values of cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut within the scope of experimental conditions.

Table 6: Response optimizer setup for cutting force in DT

SI No	v (m/min)	f (mm/rev)	d (mm)	DT (Expt)	DT (Predicted)	% of error
1	130	0.05	0.25	74.23	71.27	3.98
2	140	0.10	0.40	164.32	160.39	2.91
3	150	0.15	0.55	245.32	241.05	1.49

Table 7: Response optimizer setup for cutting force in ACT

SI No	v (m/min)	f (mm/rev)	d (mm)	DT (Expt)	DT (Predicted)	% of error
1	130	0.05	0.25	84.69	80.86	4.52
2	140	0.10	0.40	176.52	171.38	2.91
3	150	0.15	0.55	284.21	279.95	1.49

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the current work, two environmentally friendly turning circumstances are investigated: one is forced air cooling and the other is turning in a dry condition at room temperature. The studies are performed to determine how the cutting force varies in conditions

of dry turning and air cooling. In machining, prediction of the response is very important due to the experimental cost as well as time. Because of this, a model called Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is created to forecast the cutting force under the two circumstances. The results from the developed models are found to be satisfactory which can be briefly written as follows:

In comparison to ACT, the cutting force is seen to be lower in DT. The workpiece's heat softening during DT, which results in decreased cutting force during machining, is the cause.

The results of the ANOVA show that the important factors for both DT and ACT are feed rate and depth of cut. However, in both DT and ACT, the impact of depth of cut is greater than that of feed rate. It is discovered that cutting speed has very little of an impact on cutting force.

3D surface plotting and contour plotting show that cutting force increases as the feed rate and depth of cut rise. The 3D surface plot can be used to determine the ideal circumstances for determining specific cutting force values. The contour map that is produced can be thought of as an expert system for forecasting the cutting force when various feed rate and depth of cut combinations are taken into account.

For both DT and ACT, the ideal combination of cutting parameters with the response surface optimization technique is v-150 m/min, f- 0.05 mm/rev, and d- 0.25 mm.

Confirmatory experiments performed to demonstrate that the created mathematical models are capable of turning AISI D2 steel with an error rate under 5%.

REFERENCES

[1] D.K. Sarma, U.S. Dixit, J. Mater. Process. Technol. 190 (2007) 160-172.
 [2] A.K. Sharma, R.K. Singh, A.R. Dixit, A.K. Tiwari, J. Manuf. Proc. 30 (2007) 467-482.
 [3] M. Gunay, M.E. Korkmaz, N. Yasar, J. Manuf. Proc. 56 (2020) 678-687.
 [4] K.K. Gajrani, D. Ram, M.R. Sankar, J. Clean. Prod. 165 (2017) 1420-1435.
 [5] R. Kumar, A.K. Sahoo, P.C. Mishra, R.K. Das, S. Roy, Mater. T. Proceed. 5 (2018) 18482-18488.
 [6] M. Sarikaya, A. Gullu, J. Clean. Prod. 65 (2014) 604-616.
 [7] G. Singh, A. Kumar, V. Aggarwal, S. Singh, Mater. T. Proceed. 48(5) (2022) 1089-1094.
 [8] V. Sivalingam, Y. Zhao, R. Thulasiram, J. Sun, G. Kai, T. Nagamalai, Measurmt. 174 (2021) 109028.
 [9] A.K. Sharma, A.K. Tiwari, A.R. Dixit, R.K. Singh, Measurmt. 150 (2020) 107078.
 [10] D.L. Lalwani, N.K. Mehta, P.K. Jain, J. Mater. Process. Technol. 206 (2008) 167-179.

- [11] S.A. Bagaber, A.R. Yusoff, Measurmt. 136 (2019) 795-810.
- [12] K.K. Joshi, R. Kumar, Anurag, Proc. Manuf. 20 (2018) 350-357.
- [13] P.B. Zaman, N.R. Dhar, J. Manuf. Proc. 44 (2019) 179-196.
- [14] K.K. Gajrani, P.S. Suvin, S.K. Kailas, M.R. Sankar, Measurmt. 206 (2019) 108-123